

Commodification Study in Socio-Economic Perspective (Study Case: Ponggok Tourism Water Village, Klaten, Central Java)

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ABSTRACT: This article aims to describe commodification from the socio-economic perspective the local people in Ponggok Tourism Water Village. It employs a descriptive method to summarize data and information. Several indicators include employment opportunities, income local people, cultural life and social conflict through analysis. The results show that an expansion of employment opportunities, an increase in income and the standard of living of local people. There is a change in a person's socioeconomic status which is indirectly a result of his involvement in the tourism sector. It cannot be denied that it has also had a negative impact. Not a few residents from outside the area migrate and there are conflicts between residents. Local people life is experiencing changes towards westernization. Ponggok Village was previously known as a village that was far from hedonistic life, but now it is different following the times. Packaging local culture has also become something of global value.

KEYWORDS: Commodification, Local People, Socio-Economic.

INTRODUCTION

Tight competition in the tourism industry sector has led to Ponggok Tourism Water Village, Polanharjo District, Klaten Regency succeeding in stealing attention as a very unique and popular water tourism destination in Central Java. Ponggok Water Spring which offer various water tourism activities such as snorkeling, diving, sea walking, underwater photos and so on have attracted the attention of thousands of visitors.

Previously, it was a village far behind economically, the poorest village was even included in the Disadvantaged Village Infrastructure category. Previously it only had revenues of 80 million per year. However, in 2015 by utilizing village funds and community empowerment in developing village potential. In 2017, Ponggok Original Local Government Revenue managed to reach 14 billion per year. Making it famous as an independent and prosperous village and known as the Ponggok Tourism Water Village. Indirectly, Ponggok Village experienced to the village commodification.

Table 1. The Richest Village in Indonesia

Ranking	Village	Income
1.	Kutuh, South Kuta	50 billion/ year
2.	Ponggok, Klaten	14 billion/ year
3.	Bendar, Pati	80-100 billion/ year

The creativity of BUMDes Tirta Mandiri with collaboration the local people are a normal social phenomenon is very worthy of appreciation. Regional development through regional planning must involve the community as stakeholders. This is important because society is the main component of development (Samudro, 2006). Now, there are several umbul that have attracted many tourists. Every umbul certainly has beautiful natural views, clear air, a beautiful village atmosphere and different attractions. In this case, Ponggok Village also contributed to increasing Klaten Regency's revenue. Indonesia's BPS noted that in 2022 Klaten Regency will be ranked first in the district or city that generates the highest tourism revenue in Central Java.

The existence of a tourist village must be able to improve the socio-economic conditions in local peope (Abdulsyani, 2013). Even though the economic changes the local people are more visible, the tourism sector also brings about changes in social behavior, social values and social norms for the local people (Fyka et al., 2018). Changes in people's lives are a normal social phenomenon. This is because each individual has unlimited interests (Krisnawati et al., 2019).

30% green zone rule for new housing, undergraduate scholarships and the development of the Ponggok Water Spring to water tourist attraction. Since ancient times until now Ponggok Water Spring is still used in the “padusan” tradition because it is believed to bring its own blessings.

In 2013, Mr. Junaedhi invited all village youth to actively promote Ponggok Village and provide smartphone facilities to all village officials, such as BPD, PKK, RT and RW. Balanced with the development of Ponggok Water Spring, it also offers various water tourism activities such as snorkeling, diving, sea walking, underwater photos and others. Which has attracted the attention of thousands of visitors. BUMDes also began to explore other existing natural potential, such as: Besuki Water Spring, Sighedhang Water Spring, Ponggok Ciblon Water Spring, Paradisu Water Spring and the Galau Reservoir, which became known as the Ponggok Tourism Water Village. Each umbul designed with the own characteristics.

Finally, the Ponggok Tourism Water Village is increasingly visited by regional and foreign tourists until it is included in the category of the best National Tourism Village and making it famous as Ponggok Tourism Water Village. Besides that, Ponggok Village is able to manage village potential and sustainable development for the welfare of its community and has received several awards. Indirectly, Ponggok Village experienced to the village commodification. Initially one of the poorest villages in Indonesia, it later turned into an independent and prosperous village and became known as Ponggok Tourism Water Village.

Sosio-Economic Impact

1. Employment Opportunities

- a. Increase the traders and activity tourist.
- b. Increase the local people who are literate the business opportunities.
- c. High participation the local people in tourism activities.
- d. Many types of business activities local people.

2. Local Community Income

The increase in income occurred in various areas of local people livelihoods such as traders, tourism service workers and others. The development of the Ponggok Tourism Water Village makes a positive contribution to increasing local people income both directly and indirectly. Local people feel the benefits directly, such as increasing sales turnover for people who trade or work in the tourism sector. Meanwhile, the indirect benefits that can be felt by the local people are increasing. Increasing the selling value of land also means increasing local people investment and the welfare of local people.

This tourist attraction helps society improve skills, creativity in opening and managing the business they have built. Starting from setting the entrance price to tourist attractions is IDR 15,000.00. Fees apply for entry to the tourist attraction, rental of snorkeling equipment and underwater photography water. For rental of snorkeling equipment such as frog legs, the price is IDR 7,000.00, life jacket IDR 7,000.00, and tires IDR 5,000.00. The manager also offers snorkeling equipment packages the price is IDR 13,000.00. For underwater photography, the price is IDR 100,000.00 per hour, for half an hour the price is IDR 60,000.00.

Most visitors to the Ponggok’s Water Spring only rent waterproof bags for cellphones, and the management also provides them camera loan service that can only be used for two shots. Families in Ponggok Village are 76% investors in BUMDes Tirta Mandiri, the investment value given is approximately 5 million per family. Each family receives around IDR 400,000.00 to IDR 500,000.00 per month. The per capita income of residents in Ponggok is currently around IDR 1,500,000.00 up to IDR 2,000,000.00.

Table 2. Average Income in Each Umbul

Timing	Year	Umbul Tickets	Income per year
Before Viral	2010	IDR 5,000.00	5 Million
Viral Start	2011	IDR 10,000.00	100 Million
	2012	IDR 15,000.00	
Starting Viral	2013	IDR 15,000.00	600 – 700 Million
	2014	IDR 15,000.00	
	2015	IDR 15,000.00	
Viral	2016	IDR 15,000.00	Billion
	2017	IDR 15,000.00	
	2018	IDR 15,000.00	

Table 3. Ponggok’s Original Local Government Revenue 2018-2022

No	Year	PAD
1.	2018	IDR 297,863,372.00
2.	2019	IDR 5,565,000.00
3.	2020	IDR 388,609,599.00
4.	2021	IDR 216,600,000.00
5.	2022	IDR 334,650,448.00

Based on this table, it can also be seen that there is an increase in income from each spring and regional income every year.

3. Cultural Life

After as a tourist village, experienced several changes. Before as a tourist village, most people in Ponggok Tourism Water Village living as farmers. Then, many people changed status as a tourist village managed by BUMDes Tirta Mandiri profession as a tourist service provider or trader. The large of foreign tourists visiting makes people able to speak foreign languages, apart from that also brings up culture new because of the cultural mixing that occurs between local culture and traveler culture. Local people can introduce local culture to tourists so that local culture can be known to many people outside the region.

However, the cultural crisis in the Ponggok Village cannot be separated from the influence of globalization and modernization. Cultural convergence, as a tourist destination area that is often visited by tourists both local and foreign. People's lives, especially the younger generation, are changing towards westernization, such as long red hair, tattoos and tourist-style clothing.

Packaging local culture into something of global value, such as the cultural carnival tradition in Ponggok Village, which has now been packaged into a carnival open to the general public and lost its sacredness.

4. Social Conflict

Many young couples migrate with the main aim of increasing income and causing social conflict with local people. Young couples who migrate are more creative in developing their business because they come from the city than local people who have lived in the village for a long time.

Misunderstandings in operational management caused by uncoordinated two-way communication, such as dividing the tourists with tour guides, guiding flow, dividing homestays to be used, and distributing food preparation for guests. Even though there has been a division of tasks and agreements at the start, conflicts like this can still occur when the number of guest visits increases.

CONCLUSION

Indirectly, Ponggok Village experienced to the village commodification. Initially one of the poorest villages in Indonesia, it later turned into an independent and prosperous village and famous as Ponggok Tourism Water Village. Sustainable tourism development in Ponggok Village meets the pattern of sustainable tourism development. Social and cultural life, especially mutual cooperation, kinship and existing traditions, is still maintained even though it is visited by many tourists. Water springs that are used as tourist objects and attractions are still protected today. Meanwhile, the aspect of providing economic benefits to local communities is very satisfying. Tourism sector livelihoods are a livelihood strategy choice, that is interest to the local people. Community empowerment carried out in the planning, development and preservation processes for the development of the Ponggok Village is able to improve the standard of living and welfare of the local people. Also has negative impacts. Not a few residents from outside the area migrate and cause social conflict with local people. Especially the younger generation, is experiencing changes towards westernization. Packaging local culture into something of global value.

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